

Prof. Dr. Dario Cebic

ANALYSE

Claude Debussy - Selected works for piano (*Préludes II*)/

„Cloches à travers les feuilles“

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The Préludes are a monumental work, but not by tremendous effort of the sound and the emotions, but by the unheard-of variety of musical thoughts, which occur in a unique form. The work (bells, sounding through foliage) consists of a three-part form. The exposition (A) and the reprise are based on the tone G. The music itself, however, raises doubts about this explanation, because of a single bell tone here can be no question. Neither the texture with its three to five layers nor the tonal development with the central tones g and cis in the first section, e and b in the somewhat more moving contrast part before cis and g in the return to tempo I evoke the image of a lonely bell as a signal for that commemoration.

Ntbsp. 1: Orgelpunkt (ostinato)

Form/Shape:

A	B	A'
Takt/Bar: 1-23	Takt/Bar: 24-39	Takt/Bar: 40-49
Ohne vorzeichen/Unsigned	4 kreuz/4 cross	Ohne vorzeichen/Unsigned
Ganztonleiter (Whole – tone scale)	Pentathonik	Ganztonleiter (Whole – tone scale)

Shape:

- Main section A bars 1 - 23
B bar 24 - 39
A1 bar 40 - 49

C bar 54 - 64

- Coda last 3 bars

The piece begins without any sign, but in bar 24 the work gets the 4 Kreuzer and is suggested the work in this part in E major or in C sharp minor is composed. Thus, in bar 40, the work is again noted without an indication. Apart from tonality, a major difference is shown by the whole-tone scale (bars 1-23) as well as pentatonic in the B section.

Both sounds are specific to Debussy. One of his characteristics is the use of exotic, European "sound languages". It is unknown where Debussy won the title. Maybe it came from the idea of two sound sources, the combination of which stimulates his imagination: bells and foliage. The theme in this work is very complex. In the left hand, we find at the beginning of the work a whole-tone five-tone series, falling and rising. The right hand answered that series in counter-movement, by a scale part that, as the game instruction says. In between there are whole-tone scales in semiquaver triplets.

Ntbsp. 2: Whole-tone scales

The relationship between the pitch and rhythmic speed of a shift typical of the Javanese gamelan - the deepest instrument plays the longest notes, the next higher voice halves these values and so on to the highest layer moving in pearly cascades - is only hinted at by Debussy varies according to your own needs.

A					B	A'		
Einführung/ Introduction	I.Thema/ I.Theme	Brücke/ Bridge	II.Thema/ II. Theme	Brücke/ Bridge		I.Thema/ I. Theme	II.Thema/ II. Theme	Coda
Takt/Bar1-2	T./B. 3-8	T. 9-12	T. 13-20	T. 20-23	T. 24-29	T. 40-43	T. 44-47	Letzte 3 Takte/ Last 3 bars
				I. + II. Thema	Pentathonyk, 4 kreuz/Pentathonyk 4 cross			

But after the motif analysis it is noted that the work has a very complex structure. Also, the typical mood of the slendro, which can not actually be expressed in our sound system, at best occupies a kind of middle position between the pentatonic and the whole scale, Debussy creatively, by completing much of the first section of „Cloches à travers les feuilles“ from the second whole-tone scale, corresponding passages of the contrast section, however, developed from the pentatonic.

The three-part form is very complex and composed with specific motifs. Biggest A-part actually consists of 2 topics. The 1st theme actually starts in time. However, the bars 9 - 13 bring new material. The second theme starts in the 13th clock with a slightly faster tempo. This topic disappeared slowly in the clock 20 after which a bridge leads to the clock 24. The characteristic of this bridge is that the 1st and 2nd theme is coined together. After that, the work will be conducted in „E major“. After 7 bars the A theme returns, in a variant. The right hand spreads its scale part to quarter note, instead of the Rieselskalen it takes arpeggios. After 4 bars topic C occurs. This theme is in E major and is characterized by the twelve-beat and by Vorhalt chords in the left hand. After 7 bars a turn to B major, after 2 bars B major return to E major.

After another 7 bars of E major - Thama (C), the first theme A returns, in a new variant, with a descending eighth tone scale of the left hand extended to quarter notes. The result is a free rondo form for the piece: A-B-A-C-AB. In the E major part, the semiquaver figure is determined

quickly. The left hand also responds to fourths figures, which clumps individual notes secondarily.

- The „Cloches“, which are essentially determined by the full scale, contain a fairly long pentatonic middle section, from bar. 24, which is interspersed by numerous seconds
- with three overlapping whole - tone scale layers, „Cloches“ a variant of the beginning starts at bar 40. Some arpeggiated parallel sounds occur in bars 20-23 to the whole - tone scale
- In bars 20-23 of „Cloches“, a five-tone whole-tone section is played to diatonic, parallel chords in the upper part

Literaturverzeichnis

ARNDT, Jürgen: *Der Einfluß der javanischen Gamelan-Musik auf Kompositionen von Claude Debussy* (Europäische Hoc... : Reihe 36... ; 90) - 1993, Frankfurt am Main ; Wien [u.a.] : Lang, 1993.

ARNDT, Jürgen, *Einheitlichkeit versus Widerstreit : zwei grundsätzlich verschiedene Gestaltungsarten in der Musik Claude Debussys* (Europäische Hoc... : Reihe 36... ; 91) - 1993, Frankfurt am main ; Wien [u.a.] : Lang, 1993.

BARRAQUE, Jean, *Claude Debussy : in Selbstzeugnissen und Bilddokumenten/dargest.*, Reinbek bei Hamburg : Rowohlt, 1994.

BARRAQUE, Jean, *Claude Debussy : in Selbstzeugnissen und Bilddokumenten*, Reinbek bei Hamburg : Rowohlt, 1982.

BATHORI, Jane: *On the interpretation of the Méloides of Claude Debussy*. Preface by Darius Milhaud. Translation... - [Nachdr.], Stuyvesant, NY : Pendragon Press, 1998.

BERRY, Wallace: *Musical structure and performance / Wallace Berry* - 1989, New Haven [u.a.], Yale University Press, 1989.

BRUHN, Siglind: *Images and ideas in modern French piano music : the extra-musical subtext in piano works by Ravel, Debussy, and Messiaen*, New Haven [u.a.] : Yale University Press, 1989.

CORTOT, Alfred, *Französische Klaviermusik. 1. [Claude Debussy. César Franck. Gabriel Fauré. Emmanuel Chabrier. Paul Dukas]*, 1956.

DECSEY, Ernst, *Debussys Werke*, Graz ; Wien : Leykam; 1948.

HODEIR, André, *Since Debussy : a view of contemporary music*, Burch, Noel [Übers.], New York, NY : Grove Press, 1961.

JAROCIŃSKI, Stefan, *Debussy : impressionism and symbolism*, London : Eulenburg, 1976.

JENSEN, Eric Frederick, *Debussy, 1951 - Oxford*: Oxford Univ. Press; 2014.

KOLLERITSCH, Otto, *Verbalisierung und Sinngehalt : über semantische Tendenzen im Denken in und über Musik heute*, Wien ; Graz : Universal-Ed., 1989.

LEDERER, Victor, *Debussy : the quiet revolutionary*, New York, NY : Amadeus, 2007.

MARTE, Nicole, *Der mannigfaltige Einfluss der französischen Literatur auf den Dichter, Musikkritiker, Menschen und Musiker Claude Debussy*, 1996.

MEISTER, Barbara, *Nineteenth-century French song : Fauré, Chausson, Duparc, and Debussy*, Bloomington: Indiana Univ. Press, 1980.

NATTIEZ, Jean-Jacques, *De l'analyse taxinomique à la caractérisation stylistique ; From taxonomic analysis to stylistic characterization : Claude Debussy: Syrinx*, Montreal : Faculté de Musique Université de Montréal, [1973].

OK, Kim Hae, *Images : analytische und musikhistorische Aspekte von Claude Debussys Klavierkomposition Images I*, 1994, Wien, Hochsch. für Musik u. Darst. Kunst, Dipl.-Arb., 1994.

WEID, Jean-Noël von der, *Die Musik des 20. Jahrhunderts : von Claude Debussy bis Wolfgang Rihm* ; [ein Handbuch], Insel-Verl., 2001.